

REVIEW ARTICLE ON VICHARCHIKA***Dr. Chhaya Homkant Daini Hattimare**

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ABSTRACT

Vicharchika is a Tridosaj Vyadhi with kapha dosha predominance. Symptoms like strava, ruja, and shyava pidika are the cardinal features of Vicharchika and can be correlated to eczema. The etiological factors are varied in vicharchika, but virudha ahar and vegadharana (controlling of natural urges) are the major causative factors. Exposure to various nidanas makes twagadi dhatu dusti to become shithila and then causes Vicharchika. Ayurveda has a better approach to the disease. Using a medicinal herb combination provides significant relief from the signs and symptoms of Vicharchika, compared to modern medicine. Modern pharmacology offers a wide variety of medications to treat eczema, but it is not always possible to eliminate symptoms. Ayurveda removes the root cause by cleansing vitiated Dosha and balancing the Dosha and Dhatus. The Sneha sidda, mainly composed of tikta and katu rasa drugs, helps in reducing itching, burning, discharges, and dryness by improving the quality of rasa and rakta dhatu. Bahya Sneha reduces the rukshata of twak, which in turn may help in reducing the local inflammation, and so the snigdhta and varna of twacha may be improved.

KEYWORDS: Eczema, Vicharchika, Ayurvedic management.**INTRODUCTION**

In Ayurveda, Vicharchika is considered to be a type of Kushtha, which is a disease of the skin. Virruddha Ahar causes Agnimandya in patients. Agnimandya leads to incomplete digestion and fermentation of the food, and it produces Amotpatti, leading to Tridosh dushti and Kled formation, due to Ashrya- ashrayi sambandh, which leads to Mansa dusti, Twakdusti, Lasika dusti, and Raktadusti and causes Vicharchika. According to classical texts, Vicharchika has cardinal symptoms, i.e., Kandu (Excessive itching), Pidika (Vesicle/Boil/Pustule), Shyavata (Discoloration), Bahu-srava (Profuse oozing), Lasikasrava, Raji (Marked lining / Lichenification), Ruja (Pain), Rukshata (Excessive dryness). Vicharchika is Kapha pradhana tridoshaja vyadhi, and Rasa (Twak), Rakta, Mamsa, and Kleda (Ambu) are Dushya of it. The main causative factor for all the Roga is Agnimandhya.

MITHYA VIHARA: Sudden change from cold to hot and vice versa causes dusti in the Swedavaha srotas. Swedavaha srotas is also vitiated due to krodh, shoka & bhaya. Sweda is Snigdha and vitiates Kapha and Pitta and causes Kandu, Kotha, and Pidika. It is also

Kledakaraka, Srotoavrodhkara, which ultimately produces Kustha. It also causes dust of Medovaha srotas and creates Ama, and produces disease. Improper administration of Panchkrama may also produce Kustha.

PURVROOP OF VICHARCHIKA

There is no classical description regarding the purvarupa of vicharchika, but being a variety of Kustha, the purvarooopa of Kustha should be considered as its purvarooopa.

This can be summarized as follows.

Atisweda(excessive perspiration)

- Asweda(no perspiration)

- Vaivarnounnati (discoloration & elevation of the patches in the skin)

- Lomaharsha (horripilation) - Kandu (itching)

- Toda (pricking pain)

- Shrama

- Klama

- Kotha

- Severe pain in the vrana (early producing and delayed healing).

RUPA OF VICHARCHIKA

KANDU (PRURITIS):

PIDIKA (PAPULES):

SYAVA (BLACKISH DISCOLOURATION):

BAHUSRAVA (OOZING):

RUKSHATA (DRYNESS):

RUJA (PAIN):

SAMPRAPTIGHATAK OF VICHARCHIKA

Dosha Kaphapradhan Tridosha

Dushya Twak, Rakta, Mamsa, Lasika

Agni Jathragni & Dhatwagni

Ama Jathragnijanya & Dhatwagnijanya

Srotas Rasavaha, Raktavaha, Mamsavaha, Swedavaha

Srotodusti Sanga & Vimargamana

Sancharasthana Sira & Twak

Vyaktasthana Twak

Udbhavasthana Amasaya

Adhistan Tamra & Vedini Layer of Skin

Swabhava Chirkari

Rogamarga Bahy

CHIKITSA OF VICHARCHIKA: Chikitsa has been defined as “samprapti vighatanmev chikitsa”. It is well known that the science of Ayurveda deals with the primary aims, first to maintain health and second to cure the disease.

NIDAN PARIVARJAN: First step for management is to avoid the Nidana.

SHODHAN CHIKITSA: The therapy that aims at the radical removal of the causative factors of the disease is called Samshodhan chikitsa. Acharya Sharangdhar says that Kustha disease occurs due to Dosha bahulyata. These Doshas are Tiryakgami and very difficult to treat with Shamana chikitsa. In Vata pradhan Kustha-Sarpipana, in Slesma pradhan Kustha-Vamana, in Pitta pradhan Kustha-Virechan should be done. Prachchhana should be done in alpa dhosha kustha and Sira vyadha in mahata dosha kustha.

SNEHAN: Acharya Vagbhata says that Kustha Rogi should be given Snhepan in the stage of Purvarupa. The dose of Sneha is explained based on the capacity of an individual to digest the Sneha in a specific time. Charaka advises Madhyama matra.

SWEDANA: Swedana is given by Nadi Sweda or Baspa Sweda for a very short period before Shodhan. This procedure liquefies the Doshas.

SHODHANA: Kustha is Tridoshaja vyadhi. Therefore, the first prominent Dosha should be treated, then the Anubandha Dosha should be treated. When Doshas are potent, then Shodhan karma is advised. For this purpose, Rakta mokshana is to be done once in 6 months. Virechan is to be given once a month. Vamana is to be given once every 15 days.

BASTI

ASTHAPAN BASTI: Should be given in Vata predominance.

ANUVASANA: When there is an excess of Vayu even after Virechana and Ashthapana, or the patient is suitable for the administration of Anuvasana, then Anuvasana Basti should be administered. However, both types of Basti are contraindicated in the general indications, but depending upon the situations it can be done.

RAKTAMOKSHANA: Sushruta has described performing Siravyadha from the 5 main superficial veins. Charaka has advised Siravyadha by classical instruments, Alabu, Srunga, Jaloka, etc. NASYA: Nasya is indicated with the drugs like Saindhava, Danti, Maricha, and Pippali, etc., which are effective against Krimi, Kustha, and Kapha prakopaja vikara.

LEPANA: External application should ideally be applied when the patient of Kustha has undergone the Shodhan karma, and whose vitiated blood is removed from the lesions. External application of anti-Kustha druga will be effective in the disease. Some of the Kustha hara lepa are Chittrakadi, Trapvadi, Masyadi Lepa, etc.

SPECIFIC TREATMENT FOR VICHARCHIKA:

Aragwadhadi kashaya, Neli ghruta, Nimbadi ghruta, Khadira ghruta, Haridradi taila, Arka taila, Laghu and Maha Marichyadi taila, Visa taila, Shadbindu taila, Rasamanikya, Vicharchikahara lepa, Vidangadi churna, Karanja taila, and Kashmaryadi lepa, etc., are specific preparations mentioned in Ayurvedic texts. Drugs like Kustha, Daruharidra, Kasisa, Kampillak, Musta, Lodhra, Sarjarasa, Vidanga, Manahsila, Haratala, Karaveera Twak are used for Bahya parimarjana, especially in Vicharchika.

DISCUSSION

In this paper, there is a review of some medicinal herb sidds ghrita and tail, which were not mentioned in the text but modified accordingly for the convenience of the patient. We have also used these preparations in two patients, and there is a significant reduction in signs and symptoms of eczema. In eczema (Vicharchika), there are symptoms like itching (kandu), pustules (pidika), discharge(srava), discolouration (vaivaranya), and excessive dryness(rukshta). So, Guduchi and Nimb kalka sidda goghruta is used for abhyantar snehapan. Ghrita contains amrita (Tinospora cordifolia) and Nimb kalk(Azadirachta indica) as its main components. Guduchi possesses katu, tikta, and kashaya rasa, ushna veerya,laghu guna, and has the actions of tridosha shamana, raktaprasadana, daha shamana, and rasayana. Nimba (Azadirachta indica) has Tikta-Kashaya rasa, Katu Vipaka, Sheeta virya, Laghu Guna. It has Vrana nashak (anti-ulcer), Kaphanashak (Kapha suppressor), Graahi gunas (properties). Its leaves are Shothagna (antiinflammatory), Twakadoshar(skin purifier), Isomeldenin, Nimbin, nimbinene, nimbadiol, quercetin,

beta- sitosterol, and desacetyl nimbine are the active ingredients of Neem leaves extract. It is also a potent antimicrobial. Ghritha pacifies Vata dosha due to its snigdha guna, Pitta dosha due to its sheeta guna, Kapha dosha due to its property of samskarasya anuvartana, i.e., it also performs the actions of samskaraka dravyas like katutiktadi kaphahara dravyas, with which it is processed. It also possesses properties like Varnaprasadana, Mrudukarana, and nirvapana, i.e., dahaprashamana. Guduchi and Nimb kalsiddha ghritha, as Shamana sneha, administered in jatubhukshaavastha, i.e., at the time of hunger, circulates throughout the body and pacifies the provoked doshas. Studies on Guduchi (*Tinospora cordifolia*) have shown the stimulating effect on macrophages. The activated macrophages secrete GM-CSF (Granulocyte Macrophage- colony stimulating factor), which is a haemopoietic growth factor, which leads to leucocytosis and improved neutrophil function. This Immunomodulatory action of guduchi plays an important role in Eczema. External application of the formulation made by SIKTH, Haridra, and Til was used. SIKTH is Madhur Rasa Pradhan Dravya and sticky (Snigdha) in nature, so it helps in reducing the dryness and itching. Haridra mainly acts as a Kandughna, which is useful for the treatment of symptoms like itching. It has Katu and Tikta rasa, katu vipaka, and ushna virya. It is Kapha and Pitta shamaka. It acts as an immunomodulator. Curcumin, present in it, is a potent anti-inflammatory agent. It also improves skin complexion and colour. Til tail reduces Rukshata due to its sindha guna and maintain normal tone of skin. Due to its sukshma guna, it has a good penetration property. So, it helps in reducing the signs and symptoms of eczema. It also has the Twakprasadak and Vranashothahar properties. So there is reducing of scaling and itching. Due to Tikta Rasa, there is Shodana (cleaning). Katurasa has the properties of kushta kandu upshamana, kapha krimi visha upshamna, medsaamuphanta.

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